

Optimising thermal and irradiance conditions for enhanced oxygen production in *Tetradesmus bajacalifornicus*

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ABSTRACT

This work evaluated the effect of culture temperature and irradiance on oxygen production rate and biomass productivity of the microalga *Tetradesmus bajacalifornicus*, an understudied species with potential for different biotechnological applications. The optimal conditions to increase oxygen productivity were determined using a photorespirometer using a response surface methodology. The highest oxygen production rate ($250.0 \text{ mg O}_2 \cdot \text{g}^{-1} \cdot \text{h}^{-1}$) was achieved at $38.1 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and $500 \text{ } \mu\text{mol photons} \cdot \text{m}^{-2} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$, a value comparable to other high-performance strains. However, continuous exposure to $38.1 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for extended periods led to photodamage and culture collapse, indicating the importance of balancing peak oxygen production rates with thermal tolerance. Further experiments showed that heating the culture for 1 hour per day at $38.1 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ enhanced biomass accumulation by 12.5%, but longer exposures reduced oxygen production efficiency and growth. Milder temperatures ($29.0 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) did not alter oxygen production even with prolonged exposures, while $34.0 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ became detrimental beyond 1 h. These findings highlight the need to incorporate both temperature magnitude and exposure duration into microalgal growth models. Furthermore, *Tetradesmus bajacalifornicus* demonstrated robust adaptability to high irradiance and moderate thermal stress, making it a promising candidate for outdoor cultivation in warm, high-radiation environments.

Keywords: photorespirometry, biomass, algae, photosynthesis, renewable resources, carbon dioxide

1. Introduction

In 2024, the carbon dioxide concentration in the atmosphere measured at Mauna Loa Observatory in Hawaii, where the modern carbon dioxide record began in 1958, reached the alarming value of 422.8 ppm (https://gml.noaa.gov/webdata/ccgg/trends/co2/co2_annmean_mlo.txt). This is the highest level ever reached, representing a serious warning signal for the well-being of human future generations. It is urgent to stop emitting carbon dioxide to the atmosphere and to develop and implement strategies to capture and reuse carbon dioxide. Among the various carbon capture strategies being developed, microalgae production is considered as one of the most appealing [1–3]. Thanks to their ability to perform photosynthesis, microalgae use light energy, water and atmospheric carbon dioxide to produce oxygen and valuable biomass, with numerous potential applications [4–6].

Bioreactors are used for the cultivation of microalgae, allowing for precise control over the environmental conditions influencing the culture. On an industrial scale, raceway-type reactors are the most widely used because of their low construction and operating costs and ease of use [7,8]. However, they are constrained by light availability, and there exists a significant risk of culture contamination, given that they operate as open systems with the culture directly exposed to the atmosphere. [9]. For valuable biomass like *Haematococcus pluvialis*, which accumulates an antioxidant known as astaxanthin [10], most producers are employing closed photobioreactors located indoors where light is supplied using LEDs. The same strategy can be followed to produce other strains that accumulate a valuable biomolecule or by companies willing to produce microalgae in locations where the environmental conditions are suboptimal. The use of artificial illumination to produce microalgae is relatively new. It allows a more precise

control over the culture's illumination, with a fine regulation for the maintenance of optimal productive conditions. In this way, the energetic cost of illumination can be compensated by a higher quality biomass thanks to a more precise control of the culture parameters, like pH, temperature, and obviously light intensity and quality [11].

To produce biomass using artificial illumination, it is important to understand the influence of light on cell growth as high irradiances can cause photoinhibition [12]. In addition, it is also important to control illumination because while LEDs are efficient at converting electrical energy into light, part of it is lost as heat [13]. The heat generated by LEDs is dissipated into the surroundings and can lead to an overheating of the culture [14]. This is common in large artificially illuminated photobioreactors. While heating might improve the biomass productivity, an extreme temperature or a long heating time can cause a reversible or irreversible damage to the cells causing death and a culture crash [15]. Temperature plays a key role in microalgae cultures making temperature exposure duration a practical concern for upscaling. Each strain has its own optimal growth conditions. Characterising the growth conditions of a strain allows one to maximise cell growth and consequently biomass productivity. Understanding the effect of temperature on growth is also relevant for biomass production outdoors given that thermal tolerance aligns with real-world outdoor temperature fluctuations. A powerful tool that can be used to characterise microalgae is photorespirometry. This technology allows one to observe the impact of different variables on microalgal cells by measuring oxygen production, which is a main product of photosynthesis [16].

Although there are thousands of microalgal strains accessible in culture collections globally, detailed studies have been conducted on only a limited number of them. These include *Arthrospira platensis* (Spirulina), *Chlorella vulgaris*, *Haematococcus pluvialis*, *Dunaliella salina*, or *Nannochloropsis gaditana*. *Tetradasmus*

bajacalifornicus is a fast-growing microalga that can easily adapt to harsh environments and has been used as a source of compounds with *in vitro* antidiabetic, antioxidant, anti-inflammatory and antimicrobial activities [17]. *Tetradesmus bajacalifornicus* can also tolerate high levels of carbon dioxide, being an ideal species for carbon sequestration [18] and can accumulate lipids, being a potential feedstock to produce biofuels [19]. However, while these studies demonstrated its biotechnological potential, no studies have evaluated the interactive effects of temperature, irradiance, and exposure duration on its oxygen production rate, a key gap for optimising biomass productivity. Given its industrial potential and the limited information accessible in current literature, this study employed photorespirometry to examine how temperature and light affect the oxygen production rate and growth of *Tetradesmus bajacalifornicus*. Additionally, the research aimed to evaluate how the duration of heating impacts the oxygen production ability and growth of this promising microalga. Response surface methodology (RSM) was selected as a strategy to evaluate the individual factors and their significant interactions governing microalgal growth. RSM represents a powerful tool that integrates statistical parameters and graphical interpretations for the assessment of non-linear parameter interactions which could be difficult to study with a single-factor experimental approach.

2. Materials and methods

2.1 Microalga used

The microalga used was *Tetradesmus bajacalifornicus* BEA 0745-B, a microalga available at the Spanish Bank of Algae, Spain. The culture inoculum was prepared in 2 L bubble columns with constant air injection at 0.15 v/v/min and subjected to

illumination at $200 \mu\text{mol photons}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$. The pH level was maintained at 8.0 using pure carbon dioxide. The culture medium formulated for the inoculum preparation was described elsewhere [20]. The medium composition was $0.80 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1} \text{ Ca}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, $0.35 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1} \text{ MgSO}_4$, $0.10 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1} \text{ KH}_2\text{PO}_4$, and $0.03 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1} \text{ CROPMIX}^\circledR$ (Cropfutura, Almeria, Spain). CROPMIX[®] contains boron 0.7%; copper 0.3%; copper EDTA 0.3%; iron 3.5%; iron EDDHA 3.5%; manganese 4%; manganese EDTA 4%; molybdenum 0.3%; zinc 0.7%; zinc EDTA 0.7%. The inocula were prepared in triplicate using three independent bubble columns, being each bubble column the experimental unit.

2.2 Photorespirometry

Photorespirometric measurements were performed following the protocol developed in a previous study [16]. Culture volumes of 80 mL were placed into 100 mL jacketed cylindrical reactors, maintained under constant stirring. Online monitoring and regulation were applied to parameters such as temperature, dissolved oxygen levels, pH, and incident light intensity. The latter was adjusted to reach the desired average irradiance inside the culture (I_{av}), which is a function of the biomass concentration according to the formula:

$$I_{av}(\mu\text{mol}_{photons} \cdot \text{m}^{-2} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}) = \frac{I_0}{p \cdot C_b \cdot K_a} \cdot (1 - e^{-(p \cdot C_b \cdot K_a)})$$

where I_0 is the external irradiance, p the light path, C_b the biomass concentration and K_a the extinction coefficient of the biomass. This coefficient was calculated as describes in previous work [7] using the equation:

$$K_a = \frac{OD}{C_b \cdot p}$$

where OD is the optical density (400-700 nm), p the light path, and C_b the biomass concentration.

A photorespirometry experiment consisted of five cycles of measurements for every temperature condition tested, with approximately 6 minutes of aeration between each cycle. A single cycle consisted of alternating 4-minute periods of illumination and darkness. In the light phase, photosynthesis' oxygen output was recorded, while the dark phase involved quantifying the oxygen uptake by natural respiration. The apparatus facilitates the calculation of the net oxygen production rate (OPR) by deducting the oxygen consumption rate during darkness from the oxygen generation rate during illumination. The OPR was determined in triplicate per natural replicate.

2.3 Photobioreactors used and biomass production

The biomass cultivation took place in jacketed bubble columns measuring 30 cm in height and 4 cm in diameter, with a working capacity of 0.25 L. Air was introduced at the base of the reactors at a rate of 0.15 v/v/min, with temperature regulation achieved via a CORIO C-B19 water bath (Julabo GmbH, Germany). Illumination followed a 12:12 hour light:dark regimen, provided by multiple white LEDs strips (Leroy Merlin, Spain) positioned 4 cm away from the reactor surfaces. When all the LEDs were on, the average light intensity I_{av} at the centre of the photobioreactors in the absence of cells was $1,550.4 \mu\text{mol photons}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$. By adjusting the intensity of the lights, the target I_{av} was controlled. However, when microalgae self-shading did not allow this, the intensity was set at its maximum. Light irradiance measurements were conducted using an SQS100 spherical quantum sensor (Walz GmbH, Germany). The culture medium used for the biomass production was the same as that described in the previous paragraph. The biomass production was done in batch mode using three

independent photobioreactors as experimental units. All of them were operated in parallel under the same identical temperature, aeration, pH and illumination conditions.

Culture growth was monitored daily by measuring the maximum quantum efficiency of photosystem PSII (Fv/Fm) and the optical density. For each natural replicate (photobioreactor), the Fv/Fm ratio and the optical density of the culture on the whole spectrum, from 400 to 700 nm, were measured in duplicate every day. A linear correlation between the absorbance at 680 nm and the biomass concentration was made using cultures of *Tetradesmus bajacalifornicus* at different concentrations ($R^2=0.9930$). The standard curve equation obtained was:

$$C_b (g \cdot L^{-1}) = 0.818 \cdot Abs_{680nm}$$

where C_b is the biomass concentration and Abs_{680nm} the absorbance at 680 nm. The biomass concentration was determined by gravimetric analysis, which involved filtering 50 mL of the culture through 0.2 μm filters, rinsing with an equal volume of distilled water, and then drying in an oven at 70 °C for 24 h. The biomass concentration was determined in triplicate per natural replicate.

The specific growth rate was calculated using the equation [21]:

$$\mu(day^{-1}) = \frac{\ln \frac{C}{C_0}}{t - t_0}$$

where C and C_0 are the biomass concentration at the time t and t_0 , respectively. In addition, the biomass productivity was calculated using the equation:

$$P_b = \frac{C - C_0}{t - t_0}$$

where C and C_0 are the biomass concentration at the time t and t_0 , respectively.

2.4 Optimisation

The optimal combination of I_{av} and temperature for optimising the OPR was identified through RSM utilizing a central composite face-centered design. The independent variables, I_{av} and culture temperature, were adjusted within the limits of 100–600 $\mu\text{mol photons}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$ and 15–40 °C, respectively. Four factorial points and four axial points were selected. The central point was repeated three times to quantify pure error, test for curvature, and ensure the stability of the model. All the experimental runs were determined in triplicate per natural replicate, and three natural replicates (photobioreactors) were used per experimental run. These parameters were chosen to mimic typical conditions found in an indoor, artificially lit photobioreactor. The relationship between the independent variables and OPR was modelled using a polynomial response surface as outlined elsewhere [5]. After conducting an analysis of variance (ANOVA), only terms with statistical significance ($p < 0.05$) were included in the final polynomial model. The model was developed using the Design-Expert v11.0 software package (Stat-Ease Inc., USA). The model was then validated using 5 points that were assessed in triplicate; the temperature and I_{av} conditions used for model validation were: (1) 33.7 °C and 225 $\mu\text{mol photons}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$, (2) 33.7 °C and 475 $\mu\text{mol photons}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$, (3) 27.5 °C and 350 $\mu\text{mol photons}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$, (4) 21.2 °C and 225 $\mu\text{mol photons}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$, and (5) 21.2 °C and 475 $\mu\text{mol photons}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$.

2.5 Statistical analysis

For the RSM, a reduced quadratic model was used to evaluate the influence of I_{av} and temperature on the OPR. The model was refined by including only terms with statistical significance ($p < 0.05$). The fit statistics for the RSM were computed using Design-Expert v11.0 software package (Stat-Ease Inc., USA). For the statistical analysis of experimental samples produced at varying temperatures, a one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's post-hoc test were carried out using Statgraphics 19 Centurion (Statgraphics Technologies Inc., USA).

3. Results and discussion

Initially, the goal was to determine the optimal parameters to enhance the OPR using an RSM. The outcomes of this RSM can be found in Table 1 and Figure 1A. The ANOVA and fit statistics indicate that the RSM is highly significant and well-fitted to the data in the design space. The model explains 96.02% of the variability in the response ($R^2 = 0.9602$) and the adjusted R^2 was 0.9337, confirming a strong explanatory power. The predicted R^2 was 0.8753, slightly lower but still acceptable. This indicates a reasonable predictive capability. In this study both, I_{av} and temperature significantly affected the response, with temperature being the most influential factor ($p < 0.0001$). Additionally, the interaction between I_{av} and temperature, as well as the quadratic effect of I_{av} , are statistically significant, suggesting important nonlinear and interaction effects in the system (Table 1). The absence of a significant lack of fit suggests that the model effectively describes the experimental data. Overall, the model is statistically robust, fits the data well, and is suitable for optimisation and prediction within the design space. Based on the fitted results, the final regression equation in terms of actual units is as follows:

$$OPR \left(\frac{mg_{O_2}}{g_b \cdot h} \right) = -76.8282 + 0.3719 \cdot I_{av} + 3.6366 \cdot T + 0.0079 \cdot I_{av} \cdot T - 0.0006 \cdot I_{av}^2$$

The model was then validated using five random combinations within the design space (Figure 1B; $R^2=0.9317$). The model predicted the optimal combination of temperature and I_{av} for *Tetradesmus bajacalifornicus* to maximise the OPR were 38.1 °C and 500 $\mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$, respectively. These values led to an oxygen production rate of 250.0 $\text{mg}_{O_2}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$ (248.2 $\text{mg}_{O_2}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$ predicted). Figure 1A is the representation of the model, showing the theoretical tendency that higher temperature and irradiance correspond to the highest OPR values. However, it is necessary to consider the effect of such high parameters on cells vitality. For this reason, the temperature upper limit was set on 40 °C since higher temperature (45 °C) led to cell death and no oxygen production (data not shown) and was therefore left out of the model. Overall, temperatures higher than 30 °C promoted oxygen production. The same happened with I_{av} , where values higher than 250 $\mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$ led to higher OPR, until the photosaturation limit was reached. This was the first time that the oxygen production capacity of this strain was investigated. However, there are numerous studies on the oxygen production capacity that concern other species of microalgae. For example, when exposed to a light irradiance of 500 $\mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$, *Chlorella pyrenoidosa* reached an oxygen production rate of 136.39 $\mu\text{molO}_2\cdot\text{mg}^{-1}\text{Chla}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$ [22]. A study carried out using *Nannochloropsis sp.* reported a production of 100 $\text{mg}_{O_2}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$ [23], while the same photorespirometry analysis performed on *Scenedesmus almeriensis* showed a maximum oxygen production rate at 246.23 $\text{mg}_{O_2}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$ [15]. It is known that the maximum oxygen production capacity is strain-dependent. The results obtained in this study were higher than those of previous work because the combination of irradiance and temperature were optimised to maximise the oxygen production rate. The values

reported herein were in line with those of *Scenedesmus almeriensis*. *Tetradesmus* and *Scenedesmus* are two genera of the same family *Scenedesmaceae*, thus comparing high similarity even from a genetical point of view. The two strains should have similar behaviour when exposed to the same conditions [24]. Based on the results and the ability of the strain to cope with a wide range of irradiance and temperature, *Tetradesmus bajacalifornicus* can be considered a robust species for outdoor productions using open systems such as *Scenedesmus almeriensis* [25].

Once the optimal light and temperature conditions to maximise the oxygen production rate were defined, the objective of this study was to verify how these parameters affect the biomass productivity. The biomass was produced using controlled bubble columns provided with the optimal I_{av} of $500 \mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$ (or $I_0 = 1,550.4 \mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$) and maintained at two different temperatures, 25.0 and 38.1 °C during the illuminated period (12 h per day). Results are shown in Figure 2A. At 25 °C the cells were able to grow reaching a concentration of $1.6 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$. The biomass concentration reached in this study is higher than that reported for the same strain, cultured at the same temperature, but exposed to an irradiation of $180 \mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$. In that study, the biomass concentration reached $0.85 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$, suggesting that light might have been a limiting factor [26]. The results also demonstrated that *Tetradesmus bajacalifornicus* can cope with high irradiances, which suggests that this strain could be produced in locations where the solar radiation is high and using photobioreactors with a low culture depth such as thin-layer cascade photobioreactors. In turn, when cultivated at 38.1 °C, the culture crashed just three days after inoculation, as indicated by the F_v/f_m parameter that fall from the initial value of 0.71 ± 0.02 to 0.23 ± 0.02 . This finding highlighted that although this temperature is the optimal for the microalga to produce oxygen at a high rate, it does not guarantee optimal biomass growth, which is also

influenced by other parameters. The observed reduction in Fv/Fm was due to the negative effect of high temperatures on the photosynthetic apparatus, especially on the Photosystem II, which is considered the most thermosensitive complex. Thermal stress can damage the D1 protein, a crucial component of the photosystem. D1 forms a heterodimer with D2, representing the reaction centre of the system that facilitates the light-driven electron transfer, water splitting, and oxygen production. Damages to D1 lead to the disruption of the electron transport chain which cause an overflow of excess energy that generates harmful reactive oxygen species. Photosystem II impairment is generally reversible; only extreme temperatures or prolonged exposure times cause irreversible damage [27].

Similar findings were reported in an earlier investigation involving the microalga *Scenedesmus almeriensis*. The researchers found that although the ideal temperature for maximizing oxygen production was approximately 39 °C, the cells could only cope with this temperature for up to approximately 1 h [5]. In fact, exposing cells of *Scenedesmus almeriensis* to 39 °C for 2 h resulted in reversible harm to the photosynthetic apparatus, while extended exposure caused irreversible damage, hindering growth. Temperature significantly influences many biomass characteristics from growth to composition (e.g., lipid contents); this effect has been shown to be species-dependent [28]. Every species has its own optimal temperature at which it has the highest OPR. *Nannochloropsis gaditana* has its optimum at around 30 °C [23], *Picochlorum spp.* at 38 °C [29], and *Scenedesmus almeriensis* at around 35°C [30]. However, temperature alone can be misleading since microalgae cannot sustain such high values for long time periods [15]. Therefore, in this study, the exposure duration was also taken into consideration.

For microalgae, an increase of 5-10 °C compared to their optimal temperature represents a source of stress that activates several molecular mechanisms to resist the adverse conditions [31]. While microalgal consortia, which naturally occur in ecosystems, exhibit greater adaptability and resilience, in the case of monocultures the effects of high temperatures may have a stronger impact on its physiology [32]. Heat affects different elements of the cell, like membranes or proteins. Membranes lose their rigidity, becoming more fluid and consequently less resistant, while proteins can suffer structural risks, like denaturation or incorrect folding, thus altering the cell's metabolic pathways. It is also known that to maintain the proper consistency of the membranes, microalgae exposed to excessive heat change their lipid metabolism, orienting it towards the production of saturated fatty acids. Fatty acids are the main structural components of biological membranes, and their level of saturation confers a greater or lesser degree of fluidity to the membrane itself [33]. To safeguard proteins homeostasis, instead, the expression of molecular chaperones is induced. These chaperones are a group of proteins with different molecular weights commonly known as heat shock proteins. Their role is to help other proteins to maintain their conformation, thus avoiding structural damages or biochemical malfunctioning. Heat shock proteins are reported to intervene in the protection of the photosystem II in *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii* and *Dunaliella salina* [34,35]. The expression of ubiquitin and proteasome also increases under stress conditions to degrade the proteins that cannot resist the stress. When the unfavourable conditions persist, an extreme measure is the reduction of the protein synthesis to avoid the generation of incorrect proteins [31]. For these reasons, it is not possible to separate the temperature and the exposure time, and the data obtained in this study confirms this.

Figure 2B, shows that *Tetradesmus bajacalifornicus* could produce oxygen at its maximum rate during the first hour of exposure at 38.1 °C. Then, its oxygen production rate rapidly fell to a minimum of 48 mg_{O₂}·g⁻¹·h⁻¹, almost half the rate of the culture kept at 25.0 °C. This suggested that the cells sustained significant damage, compromising their photosynthetic capacity thus explaining the culture crash observed after three days. This was not assessed before, except for the above-mentioned study using *S. almeriensis* where the authors observed that more than 1 h of heating led to photosynthetic damage [15]. The results reported in this study support that previous work and highlight the importance of including time of exposure to heat into growth models, which is, to the best of the authors knowledge, not being considered. These results are also in line with other study where the response of *Chlorella saccharophila* to heat stress was evaluated. Up to 40 °C, the cells did not suffer any relevant damage; however, for higher temperatures, the exposure time became significant. Two hours at 44.0 °C were sufficient to induce a significant cell death rate [36].

To further explore the relationship between temperature and exposure time a new series of experiments were performed. In the first ones, the culture was either kept at 25.0 °C during the whole day or heated at 38.1 °C for only a limited number of hours per day. An analogous study utilizing a different strain demonstrated that daily exposure to the optimal temperature for 1 h enhanced the system's oxygen production capacity from 3129.5 mg_{oxygen}·g_{biomass}⁻¹ to 3778.5 mg_{oxygen}·g_{biomass}⁻¹ [15]. Figure 3A demonstrate a similar pattern for *Tetradesmus bajacalifornicus*. Heating the culture during 1 h had a positive effect on the culture, allowing to reach a biomass concentration of 1.8 g·L⁻¹, significantly higher than that of the control at 25.0 °C (*p*<0.05). In turn, an exposure time of 2 h reduced the growth capacity of the cells. The cells did not suffer irreversible damages, like it occurred when the culture was exposed

to heat for 3 h per day. The latter crushed after 10 days from inoculation. Respirometric results, shown in Figure 3B, confirmed these findings, showing that cells heated for 2 or 3 h per day suffered a significant reduction in their oxygen production rate, from around $100 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$ to approximately $70 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$. The photorespirometric results and those obtained from the bubble columns are consistent and demonstrate that although the cells can produce oxygen at their maximum rate at $38.1 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, the exposure to this temperature for more than 1 h can damage the cells and limit both, oxygen production capacity and growth.

The last experiments performed in this study consisted of assessing the effect of milder temperatures during longer exposure times (1-4 h). Figure 4A and Figure 4B show the results observed at 29.0 and $34.0 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The oxygen production rate did not reach the maximum level of $250 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$, obtained at the optimal temperature described above. Figure 4A shows that *Tetradesmus bajacalifornicus* does not suffer any significant damage regardless of the duration of heating at $29.0 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ (up to 4 h), being able to return to the initial OPR. In the case of $34.0 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, however, the microalga was able to tolerate this temperature for just 1 h without suffering damage. Exposure to $34.0 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for more than 1 h affected the cells that were no longer able to reach the initial OPR. As the temperature was lower, damage was less than that reported after exposure to $38.1 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. Figure 5 shows how oxygen production decreased when the microalgae was exposed to high temperatures for more than two hours, confirming both the experimental data and the findings in the literature reported in this work. Based on the findings reported herein, the microalga *Tetradesmus bajacalifornicus* studied showed potential for being produced in regions with a high solar radiation and where the temperature is mild, as its photosynthetic capacity might be affected if the temperature of the culture reaches $34 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for more than 1 h per day.

4. Conclusions

The results of this study demonstrate that *Tetradesmus bajacalifornicus* possesses a high oxygen production capacity under optimal temperature and irradiance conditions, with an OPR that compares favourably with industrially relevant strains. However, while 38.1 °C is optimal for short-term oxygen production, sustained exposure at this temperature significantly affects the oxygen production rate and leads to culture collapse. Short daily heating periods (up to 1 hour) at high temperatures can enhance biomass productivity without causing irreversible damage, while longer durations result in metabolic stress and decreased performance. Milder temperatures, particularly 29.0 °C, allow for longer exposure without detriment to the cells, suggesting a better balance between productivity and stability. These findings emphasise the importance of incorporating temperature exposure time into microalgal cultivation strategies. While this type of control is easier to implement in closed reactors with artificial light, that can be easily regulated according to the system temperature, it is more challenging in facilities using open reactors. In this second case a careful planning of the reactor construction site becomes essential. Common strategies include building the reactors into greenhouse or using heat exchanger to cool down or raise the culture temperature as required. However, these approaches may have other drawbacks like a light reduction in the green house or increased maintenance costs for the exchanger. Therefore, the selection of the species to be cultivated, which should be adapted to high temperatures, is suggested to be an important factor for achieving effective cultivation. Overall, *Tetradesmus bajacalifornicus* shows strong potential for high-efficiency, scalable biomass and

oxygen production, especially in settings with high solar radiation and moderate thermal fluctuations.

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CRedit Contributor Roles

S. Villaró: Investigation, Formal analysis, and Writing – Original draft; **C. Cerdá-Moreno:** Investigation, Formal analysis, and Writing – Original draft; **E. Viviano:** Formal analysis, Writing – Original draft; **J. Tripiana:** Investigation; **S. Triviño de las Heras:** Investigation; **M. Salinas-García:** Investigation; **T. Lafarga:** Writing – Review & editing, Supervision and Funding acquisition.

Conflict of interests

Authors declare no conflicts of interests

Data availability statement

The authors declare that the data supporting the findings of this study are available within the paper. Should any raw data files be needed in another format they are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Table 1. ANOVA results and fit statistics for the predictive reduced quadratic model used for OPR optimisation.

Source	Sum of squares	df	Mean square	F-value	p-value	Fit statistics	
Model	57812.77	4	14453.19	36.23	0.0002	SD	19.97
A (I_{av})	12990.25	1	12990.25	32.57	0.0013	Mean	139.51
B (Temperature)	38762.45	1	38762.45	97.19	<0.0001	C.V. (%)	14.32
AB	2488.51	1	2488.51	6.24	0.0467	R ²	0.9602
A ²	3571.56	1	3571.56	8.95	0.0242	Adjusted R ²	0.9337
Residual	2392.29	6	398.88			Predicted R ²	0.8753
Lack of Fit	2235.02	4	558.76	7.06	0.1279	AP	18.8497
Pure Error	158.27	2	79.13				
CT	60206.06	10					

Abbreviations: CT, corrected total; SD, standard deviation; CV, coefficient of variation; AP, adequate precision. R² represents the proportion of total variation in the response data that is explained by the model.

Figure legends

Figure 1. (A) Predictive reduced quadratic model showing the interactive effects of temperature and irradiance on the OPR and (B) model validation: linear regression analysis comparing OPR values predicted by the RSM against independent experimental results.

Figure 2. Effect of constant heating at 38.1 °C on (A) the biomass concentration and (B) the oxygen production rate of *T. bajacalifornicus*.

Figure 3. Effect of heating during 1-3 h at 38.1 °C on (A) the biomass concentration and (B) the oxygen production rate of *T. bajacalifornicus*. The graph shows the mean value of three independent determinations \pm SD.

Figure 4. Effect of heating during 1-4 h at 29.0 or 34.0 °C on the oxygen production rate of *T. bajacalifornicus*. The graph shows the mean value of three independent determinations.

Figure 5. Effect of heating duration and temperature on the daily oxygen production capacity of *T. bajacalifornicus*.

Figure 1

(A)

(B)

Figure 2

(A)

(B)

Figure 3

(A)

(B)

Figure 4

(A)

(B)

Figure 5

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